

Appendix E

Additional information on statistical analyses

General information on statistical analysis

All data analyses were performed with R (RStudio Team, 2018, version 3.5.1). The power of the hypotheses was calculated using G*Power 3 (Faul et al., 2007) and the Monte Carlo power analysis for indirect effects (Schoemann et al., 2017). For every analysis, including tests to check assumptions, the significance level was set to .05. To check if manipulations work, two three-way mixed analyses of variance (ANOVAs; DVs: attributed crisis responsibility or perceived humor; between factors AV1: crisis responsibility; AV2: framing; within factor AV 3: scenario) were conducted. The main effect of crisis responsibility was considered in the first ANOVA to check if the manipulation of crisis responsibility worked. The main effect of framing was focused on in the second ANOVA to evaluate if the manipulation of humor worked. The other respective variable, as well as the presented scenario, were included as control variables. The effect sizes for the mixed ANOVAs were reported as partial Eta-squared.

H1a-c and H2a-c as well as RQ1-RQ3 were examined by using two 2X2 multivariate analyses of variance (MANOVAs; MANOVA 1: DVs: trust, negative affect, positive affect; AV1: crisis responsibility; AV2: framing; MANOVA 2: DVs: behavioral intention variables; AV1: crisis responsibility; AV2: framing). Whenever the MANOVAs yielded significant overall results, corresponding separate follow-up ANOVAs for the individual DVs were conducted. As it was decided to conduct MANOVAs to avoid an inflation of Type I errors, the follow-up ANOVAs were subsequently not Bonferroni-corrected, avoiding type II errors and a loss in power (Field et al., 2012). The main effects of crisis responsibility were relevant to the evaluation of H1a-c and RQ2. The main effects of crisis response strategy's framing were critical to evaluate H2a-c and RQ3. The crisis responsibility by crisis response strategy's framing interactions were relevant to the evaluation of RQ1. The effect sizes for the MANOVAs as well as the ANOVAs were reported as partial Eta-squared.

H1d and H2d as well as RQ4 and RQ5 were tested using separate mediation analyses, two for trust and the others for behavioral intentions variables, following the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression procedures for mediation (see Baron & Kenny, 1986). Due to results given in the precedent ANOVAs, simple instead of planned parallel mediation analyses were conducted as it was shown that not both independent variables influenced both positive and negative affect significantly. When none of the independent variables influenced the respective outcome variable significantly, mediation analyses were omitted. Otherwise, two linear regression models were fitted for each independent variable: A mediation model to predict the mediator (positive or negative affect) and an outcome model to predict trust or the behavioral intentions variables. In both models we controlled for the other respective independent variable (framing or crisis responsibility). Both crisis responsibility and framing were coded as dummy variables, the low responsibility condition and the rational framing were chosen as reference variables, respectively. Using the R package *mediation* (Tingley et al., 2014) the average causal mediation effect (ACME) was estimated and tested for significance via bca-corrected bootstrapping (Efron, 1979) using 1000 simulations in each mediation analysis. Due to missing

consensus on the calculation of effect sizes in mediation models and their interpretation (see Preacher & Kelley, 2011) it was decided to not report any effect size for the indirect effect.

Additionally, four explorative analyses were examined. In the first explorative analysis, a series of hierarchical regression was used to predict trust, negative affect or positive affect using both independent variables (step 1), demographics (step 2), participants' sense of humor and disposition to trust (step 3). In the second exploratory analysis, we examined the moderating influence of participants' age, sex, work area, disposition to trust, or sense of humor on the effect of crisis responsibility or the crisis response strategy's framing on trust using moderated OLS regression analyses, following the procedure recommended by Aiken and West (1991; see also Cohen et al., 2003). In these regression analyses, both crisis responsibility and framing were coded as dummy variables, the low responsibility condition and the rational framing were chosen as reference variables. Effect sizes were reported as standardized regression coefficients. We ran a third exploratory analysis to examine the effect of both experimental manipulations on participants' liking of the local government's tweet, using a two-way ANOVA. In the fourth exploratory analysis, we conducted a mixed ANOVA to examine the between-subjects effect of the experimental manipulations, the within-subjects effect of scenario on trust and their interaction effect. The effect sizes of the ANOVAs were reported as partial Eta-squared.

Before calculating the ANOVAs, MANOVAs and regression analyses, necessary assumptions were checked. In the mixed ANOVAs, degrees of freedom were corrected using Huynh-Feldt estimates of sphericity, if the assumption of sphericity was not met. In the MANOVAs, Pillai's trace was used as test statistics, if violations of multivariate normality or homogeneity of covariance matrices were detected. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) this test statistic is the most robust statistic for general protection against departures from the multivariate normality and homogeneity of variance-covariance matrices. The ANOVAs were White-adjusted if the assumption of homoscedasticity was violated. However, even in cases where the assumption of normal distribution was not met, ANOVAs were conducted without any correction as they are relatively robust when the sample size is above 30 and when participants are equally distributed among the experimental conditions (Schmider et al., 2010).

Additional data and results

Results of the manipulation checks and descriptive data of all measures used are displayed in table E1 and table E2, respectively. Table E3 illustrates the follow-up ANOVAs for all behavioral intentions variables.

Table E1*ANOVA summary table for the manipulation checks*

Measure	Factor	df_{Num}	df_{Den}	F	p	η_p^2
Attributed crisis responsibility	CR	1	513	495.90	< .001***	.49
	Framing	1	513	1.30	.255	< .01
	CR x framing	1	513	0.01	.942	< .01
	Scenario	1.87	960.45	12.54	< .001***	.02
	CR x scenario	1.87	960.45	34.37	< .001***	.06
	Framing x scenario	1.87	960.45	0.08	.920	< .01
	CR x framing x scenario	1.87	960.45	0.07	.932	< .01
Perceived humor	CR	1	513	0.08	.781	< .01
	Framing	1	513	356.25	< .001***	.41
	CR x framing	1	513	0.01	.941	< .01
	Scenario	2	1026	115.41	< .001***	.18
	CR x scenario	2	1026	2.11	.122	< .01
	Framing x scenario	2	1026	34.46	< .001***	.06
	CR x framing x scenario	2	1026	1.35	.259	< .01

Note. df_{Num} = degree of freedom numerator. df_{Den} = degrees of freedom denominator. CR = crisis responsibility. The between-subjects factors crisis responsibility and framing had two levels (high vs. low or humorous vs. rational), respectively. The within-subjects factor had three levels (scenario 1, scenario 2, scenario 3).

*** $p < .001$.

Table E2*Descriptive data of all measures*

Measure	Framing	Crisis responsibility				Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	
		High (<i>n</i> = 262)		Low (<i>n</i> = 255)			
		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Attributed crisis responsibility ^a	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	5.55	0.94	3.38	1.31	4.52	1.57
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	5.67	0.94	3.49	1.21	4.56	1.54
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	5.61	0.94	3.44	1.26	4.54	1.55
Perceived humor ^a	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	4.24	1.17	4.27	1.28	4.25	1.22
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	2.22	1.18	2.24	1.24	2.23	1.21
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	3.23	1.55	3.19	1.61	3.21	1.58
Trust	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	4.32	0.96	4.75	0.91	4.53	0.96
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	4.69	1.05	4.80	0.99	4.75	1.02
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	4.51	1.02	4.78	0.95	4.64	1.00
Negative affect	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	1.59	0.43	1.50	0.45	1.55	0.44
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	1.67	0.48	1.48	0.43	1.57	0.47
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	1.63	0.46	1.49	0.44	1.56	0.45
Positive affect	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	2.09	0.83	2.26	0.81	2.17	0.83
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	2.31	0.78	2.40	0.85	2.35	0.82
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	2.20	0.81	2.34	0.84	2.27	0.83
Willingness to follow advice							
I would follow local government's advice in a crisis.	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	4.79	1.00	5.08	1.04	4.93	1.02
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	5.01	1.07	5.20	1.04	5.10	1.06
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	4.90	1.04	5.15	1.04	5.02	1.05
As a matter of principle, I would not follow advice from the local government in a crisis. ^b	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	5.71	1.15	5.85	1.28	5.78	1.21
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	5.45	1.52	5.92	1.22	5.69	1.39
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	5.58	1.35	5.89	1.25	5.73	1.31
Secondary crisis communication							
I would tell family and friends about the local government's tweet.	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	5.07	1.28	5.16	1.24	5.11	1.26
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	5.26	1.15	5.21	1.19	5.23	1.17
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	5.17	1.22	5.18	1.21	5.17	1.22
I would ask family and friends to follow the advice given by the local government in a crisis situation.	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	4.47	1.23	4.72	1.28	4.59	1.26
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	4.73	1.24	4.93	1.13	4.83	1.19
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	4.60	1.24	4.83	1.21	4.71	1.23
Willingness to seek for information							
I would visit the local government's website in a crisis situation to get more information about the crisis.	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	5.16	1.22	5.61	1.09	5.37	1.18
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	5.26	1.24	5.49	1.18	5.38	1.21
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	5.21	1.23	5.55	1.14	5.37	1.20

Measure	Framing	Crisis responsibility				Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	
		High (<i>n</i> = 262)		Low (<i>n</i> = 255)			
		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
I would visit the local government's Facebook page in a crisis situation to get more information about the crisis.	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	3.44	1.95	3.53	1.99	3.48	1.97
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	3.61	2.00	3.46	2.06	3.53	2.03
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	3.53	1.98	3.49	2.03	3.51	2.00
Liking of the tweet	Humorous (<i>n</i> = 250)	3.92	1.36	4.23	1.51	4.07	1.44
	Rational (<i>n</i> = 267)	4.42	1.21	4.41	1.25	4.42	1.23
	Σ (<i>n</i> = 517)	4.17	1.31	4.33	1.38	4.25	1.45

Note. Means and standard deviations for all measures graded by crisis responsibility (high vs. low) and framing of the crisis response strategy (humorous vs. rational) and across conditions (Σ).

^a In the interest of parsimony it was decided to only report means and standard deviations graded by both experimental conditions but not by the scenario presented, which was included as further control variable in the ANOVA conducted for the manipulation checks.

^b In the interest of consistency the reversed version of this item was used in calculations.

Table E3*ANOVA summary table for variables measuring behavioral intentions*

Measure	Factor	<i>F</i> (1, 513)	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
Willingness to follow advice				
I would follow the local government's advice in a crisis.	Crisis responsibility	7.01	.008**	.01
	Framing	3.18	.075	.01
	Interaction	0.28	.597	< .01
As a matter of principle, I would not follow advice from the local government in a crisis. ^a	Crisis responsibility	7.09	.008**	.01
	Framing	0.74	.391	< .01
	Interaction	2.17	.141	< .01
Secondary crisis communication				
I would tell family and friends about the local government's tweet.	Crisis responsibility	0.02	.891	< .01
	Framing	1.30	.254	< .01
	Interaction	0.47	.494	< .01
I would ask family and friends to follow the advice given by the local government in a crisis situation.	Crisis responsibility	4.23	.040*	.01
	Framing	4.65	.032*	.01
	Interaction	0.04	< .834	< .01
Willingness to seek for information				
I would visit the local government's website in a crisis situation to get more information about the crisis.	Crisis responsibility	10.94	.001**	.02
	Framing	0.01	.938	< .01
	Interaction	1.11	.293	< .01
I would visit the local government's Facebook page in a crisis situation to get more information about the crisis.	Crisis responsibility	0.03	.853	< .01
	Framing	0.07	.794	< .01
	Interaction	0.46	.499	< .01

Note. The between-subjects factors crisis responsibility and framing had two levels (high vs. low or humorous vs. rational), respectively. The term interaction describes the crisis responsibility x framing interaction.

^a In the interest of consistency the reversed version of this item was used in calculations.

p* < .05. *p* < .01.

Additional results of exploratory analyses

Regarding our first exploratory analysis, all significant effects were small according to Cohen, who defines $\beta < .30$ as small. The complete results of our second exploratory analysis, the moderated OLS regression analyses, are depicted in table E4. All significant interaction effects found were small according to Cohen's convention (1988). The complete results of our third exploratory analysis are shown in table E5. The main effect of crisis scenario on trust was large while the crisis scenario x crisis responsibility and crisis scenario x framing interaction effects were small according to Cohen (1988). The fourth exploratory analysis showed that the main effect of crisis responsibility on the participants' liking of the tweet was not significant, $F(1, 513) = 1.63, p = .197, \eta_p^2 < .01$. However, the ANOVA yielded a significant effect of framing, $F(1, 513) = 8.39, p = .004, \eta_p^2 = .02$, suggesting that participants preferred the rational framing ($M = 4.07, SD = 1.44$) rather than the humorous one ($M = 4.42, SD = 1.23$). According to Cohen (1988) the effect size was small. The crisis responsibility x framing interaction effect was not significant either, $F(1, 513) = 1.86, p = .173, \eta_p^2 < .01$.

Table E4

Results of the moderated OLS regression analyses

Model	Predictor	<i>b</i>	<i>SE b</i>	β	<i>R</i> ²
Model 1	Intercept	4.799***	0.084	.000	.06
	Crisis responsibility ^a	-0.103	0.119	-.052	
	Framing ^b	-0.049	0.123	-.024	
	Age ^c	-0.001	0.005	-.010	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing	-0.328	0.172	-.144	
	Crisis responsibility X Age	-0.016*	0.007	-.180	
	Framing X Age	-0.003	0.008	-.035	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing X Age	0.013	0.011	.107	
Model 2	Intercept	4.722***	0.117	-	.05
	Crisis responsibility ^a	0.033	0.163	-	
	Framing ^b	0.056	0.171	-	
	Sex_female	0.158	0.169	-	
	Sex_divers	0.056	0.702	-	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing	-0.524	0.236	-	
	Crisis responsibility X Sex_female ^c	-0.330	0.243	-	
	Crisis responsibility X Sex_divers ^c	1.189	1.210	-	
	Framing X Sex_female	-0.241	0.248	-	
	Framing X Sex_divers	1.833	1.211	-	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing X Sex_female	0.494	0.348	-	
Crisis responsibility X Framing X Sex_divers	NA	NA	NA		
Model 3	Intercept	4.809***	0.087	.000	.04
	Crisis responsibility ^a	-0.142	0.125	-.072	
	Framing ^b	-0.044	0.129	-.022	
	JC1	-0.198	0.358	-.057	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing	-0.319	0.182	-.140	
	Crisis responsibility X JC1	0.542	0.482	.119	
	Framing X JC1	0.099	0.460	.023	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing X JC1	-0.268	0.620	-.047	
Model 4	Intercept	4.798 ***	0.086	.000	.04
	Crisis responsibility ^a	-0.087	0.123	-.044	
	Framing ^b	-0.015	0.127	-.007	
	JC2 ^d	-0.004	0.380	-.001	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing	-0.348	0.178	-.152	
	Crisis responsibility X JC2	-0.462	0.587	-.073	
	Framing X JC2	-0.418	0.523	-.073	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing X JC2	0.508	0.776	.063	
Model 5	Intercept	4.799***	0.104	.000	.04
	Crisis responsibility ^a	-0.163	0.148	-.082	
	Framing ^b	-0.101	0.152	-.051	

Model	Predictor	<i>b</i>	<i>SE b</i>	β	<i>R</i> ²
	JC3 ^d	-0.005	0.177	-.002	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing	-0.138	0.214	-.060	
	Crisis responsibility X JC3	0.171	0.253	.066	
	Framing X JC3	0.174	0.260	.066	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing X JC3	-0.535	0.363	-.156	
Model 6	Intercept	4.785***	0.085	.000	.04
	Crisis responsibility	-0.119	0.122	-.060	
	Framing ^b	-0.035	0.126	-.018	
	JC4 ^d	0.548	0.572	.106	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing	-0.310	0.176	-.136	
	Crisis responsibility X JC4	0.313	0.758	.043	
	Framing X JC4	-0.473	0.688	-.074	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing X JC4	-0.302	0.943	-.033	
Model 7	Intercept	4.811***	0.081	.000	.10
	Crisis responsibility ^a	-0.140	0.116	-.071	
	Framing ^b	-0.055	0.119	-.028	
	Disposition to trust ^c	0.432***	0.107	.325	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing	-0.259	0.167	-.114	
	Crisis responsibility X Disposition to trust	-0.155	0.156	-.084	
	Framing X Disposition to trust	-0.480**	0.162	-.252	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing X Disposition to trust	0.641**	0.225	.253	
Model 8	Intercept	4.818***	0.083	.000	.07
	Crisis responsibility ^a	-0.116	0.120	-.059	
	Framing ^b	-0.085	0.122	-.043	
	Sense of humor ^c	0.128*	0.054	.206	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing	-0.336	0.172	-.147	
	Crisis responsibility X Sense of humor	-0.100	0.074	-.115	
	Framing X Sense of humor	< -0.001	0.077	< -.001	
	Crisis responsibility X Framing X Sense of humor	0.121	0.108	.093	

Note. *N* = 517. JC1 = job in local government; JC2 = job in crisis management; JC3 = job in fire brigade or rescue service; JC4 = job in police or security authorities. All significance tests were two-tailed. The four-way interaction in model 2 was not fitted due to content-wise reasons. Standardized regression coefficients could not be calculated in this model due to multicollinearity.

^a 0 = low crisis responsibility, 1 = high crisis responsibility. ^b 0 = rational framing, 1 = humorous framing. ^c Male was coded as reference category. ^d 0 = no, 1 = yes. ^e Age, disposition to trust and sense of humor were centered.

p* < .05. *p* < .01. ****p* < .001.

Table E5

ANOVA summary table for the exploratory analysis IV

Measure	Factor	<i>df</i> _{Num}	<i>df</i> _{Den}	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
Trust	CR	1	513	9.57	.002**	.02
	Framing	1	513	5.67	.018*	.01
	CR x framing	1	513	3.55	.060	.01
	Scenario	1.90	976.76	131.38	< .001***	.20
	CR x scenario	1.90	976.76	4.80	.010**	.01
	Framing x scenario	1.90	976.76	4.19	.017*	.01
	CR x framing x scenario	1.90	976.76	1.33	.265	< .01

Note. *df*_{Num} = degree of freedom numerator. *df*_{Den} = degrees of freedom denominator. CR = crisis responsibility. The between-subjects factors crisis responsibility and framing had two levels (high vs. low or humorous vs. rational), respectively. The within-subjects factor had three levels (scenario 1, scenario 2, scenario 3).

p* < .05. *p* < .01. ****p* < .001.

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